

Systematic Review: Prevalence and Concentration of Main Biological Hazards in/on Food Matrices

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1. Main Objective of the Systematic Review

The main objective of the present systematic review is to bring together and summarise, under a categorised arrangement, information and data on the occurrence (i.e., prevalence and concentration) of the most important biological hazards in various foods produced and marketed in Europe, as extracted from peer-reviewed articles.

The biological hazards (foodborne pathogens) considered are: *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia duodenalis*, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus. The foods considered are beverages, meat and meat products, eggs and egg products, milk and dairy products, seafood, produce – fruits and vegetables, cereals and composite products.

2. Protocol for the Systematic Review

2.1 Review question

The review question is: “what is the occurrence (i.e., prevalence and/or concentration) of the most important biological hazards in the various foods and food products produced and commercialised in Europe?”. The review question is of a typical *descriptive* nature as it enquires about a condition of interest (viz. contamination by foodborne pathogens) in a population of foods. This descriptive question has a simple PO structure (*population* and *outcome*) with key elements that can be broken down, as follows:

Population: Food products in general, namely, beverages, meat and meat products, eggs and egg products, milk and dairy products, seafood, produce – fruits and vegetables, cereals and composite products., produced and/or placed on the market in Europe.

Outcome: Occurrence of at least one of the following biological hazards, *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia duodenalis*, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus, expressed as either prevalence or concentration measured in the population.

Because both key elements can be clearly specified, the review question is *close-framed*, which is advantageous because it enables the setting of more clear eligibility criteria *a priori*, as opposed to open-framed questions.

2.2 Criteria for inclusion of individual studies

For a study to be included in the systematic review, it should comply with criteria at the levels of study design, population, outcomes of interest, study characteristics, type of publication and language of the full text. The eligibility criteria are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for inclusion of individual studies in the systematic review question

Type of criteria	Criteria
Study design	Occurrence data must originate from observational studies that could be cross-sectional or longitudinal where food samples have been sampled by a randomised design, either simple or stratified. These experimental designs are typically used in studies related to microbiological surveillance, microbiological characterisation of foods, and microbiological surveys in food factories, at retail or in restauration establishments.
Population	Foods, as finished product or during production/processing, must be sampled from farms, processing facilities, retail or restauration establishments located in a European country Food chain stage where samples were taken must be clearly specified.
Outcomes of interest	Occurrence data must be given for any of the following 14 biological hazards: <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> , Shiga-toxin <i>Escherichia coli</i> (STEC), <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> , <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> , <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> , <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp., <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> , Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus and Norovirus. The study must present the results on prevalence and/or enumeration of the pathogen in/on foods. For prevalence, it should provide at least sample size and number of positive samples; and for enumeration, it should provide at least the sample size, a measure of concentration, and in addition, for bacteria, it should provide or allow the calculation of the limit of quantification.
Method	The microbiological method used must be described, or alternatively a reference must be provided; and the sample size must be higher than 3 units.
Language of the full text	English, Spanish, French, Portuguese
Publication type	Primary research studies

Examples of primary studies excluded:

Primary studies not meeting the pre-set criteria will not be included in the systematic review. Examples of primary studies to be excluded are: (1) investigations of likely food vehicles within the context of food-borne outbreaks; (2) studies providing occurrence data without describing the microbiological method used or citing the method used as a source in the list of references; and (3) studies on serology prevalence of pathogens in live animals (on farm).

2.3 Searching for individual studies

The bibliographic search will be conducted using a combination of¹:

<i>General terms:</i>	sampling OR survey* OR incidence OR prevalence OR occurrence OR contamination OR level* OR concentration OR count* OR numbers OR presence OR microbiological quality OR microbiological safety
<i>Biological hazard:</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> OR <i>Campylobacter</i> OR (Escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)) OR <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> OR <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> OR <i>Bacillus cereus</i> OR <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> OR <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> OR <i>Toxoplasma</i> OR <i>Giardia</i> OR <i>Cryptosporidium</i> OR norovirus OR hepatitis A OR hepatitis E
<i>Foodstuff – beverages :</i>	beverage* OR juice* OR drink* OR bottled water
<i>Foodstuff – meat :</i>	meat OR beef OR bovine meat OR pig meat OR pork OR chicken OR broiler OR game meat OR sausage OR delicatessen meat OR deli OR poultry OR turkey OR duck
<i>Foodstuff - eggs:</i>	egg* OR egg products OR dried egg
<i>Foodstuff - dairy:</i>	dairy OR milk OR milk product OR milk powder OR powdered milk OR whey OR infant formula OR cheese OR butter OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR cream
<i>Foodstuff - seafood:</i>	seafood OR fish OR shellfish OR crustacean OR mollusc OR mollusk
<i>Foodstuff - produce:</i>	produce OR vegetable OR legume* OR salad* OR fruit* OR nuts OR seeds OR sprout* OR spice*
<i>Foodstuff - composite:</i>	composite OR composite food OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR complex food OR multi-ingredient food OR dessert

¹ Annex 1 presents the search strategies. However, in December 2021, keywords were widely extended and search strategies modified accordingly. Annex 2 presents the updated search strategies.

AND NOT: “challenge study” OR artificial OR spiked OR extract*
OR feed OR supplement* OR meta-analysis OR
“systematic review” OR review OR antimicrobial*

Primary studies will be searched from the year 2000 onwards in the e-bibliographic databases PubMed, Web of Science (Core Collection, all databases), Scopus and SciELO (see Annex 1), using the aforementioned terms duly connected (General terms AND Biological hazards AND Foodstuff NOT Terms) and in the proper database syntax. The entries will be filtered by authors’ affiliation country to keep only European countries, and then by language to keep English, Spanish, French and Portuguese. Exact search strategies, date of searches and number of records retrieved will be duly documented. The bibliographic search process in the four databases will be carried out by two researchers in parallel, who will compare the number of records recovered, which should duly match in order to proceed with the next steps. The large volume of bibliographic citations will be documented and managed in the JabRef software with direct links to the sources in PDF. A JabRef reference database will be built by biological hazard².

2.4 Deduplication of individual studies

JabRef software will be set to identify duplicate references, which will be carefully checked and deleted/merged by the two researchers. The reference databases will be managed by two senior experts in systematic reviews, who will maintain and update the databases at the different stages (i.e. raw, no duplicates, clean, following updates and definite/final for meta-analysis).

2.5 Selecting the individual studies

The selection of individual studies will be carried out by two researchers and two senior reviewers. Once all the entries have been deduplicated, relevant studies will be screened for inclusion, following four steps:

- a. *Title/abstract (Ti/Ab) screening.* Each of the titles and abstracts from the bibliographic databases will be screened for its relevance to answering the review question. Each record will be assessed by one researcher. The number of records that did not pass this first screening will be annotated.
- b. *Full-text screening.* For records that pass the Ti/Ab screening (scored either yes or unclear at Ti/Ab level), the full-text primary studies will be obtained and annexed to the JabRef databases. Each full-text reference will be screened for eligibility by one researcher, according to the inclusion criteria outlined in Section 2.4. All annotations will be digitally made on the PDF articles; and any doubts on the inclusion of a study will be resolved in the regular meetings with the senior researcher.

² In the literature search of December 2021, entries for all foodborne pathogens were kept in one single JabRef reference database.

- c. *Identification of possible duplicate publications.* Because sometimes the same study is reported or partially reported in several articles, these situations must be carefully identified to avoid double-counting. Records likely to be linked to the same study will be marked in JabRef for posterior evaluation, in discussion with one of the Senior Researchers. If the evaluation of results points towards the case of duplicate publication, the linked records will be grouped together and examined as one study unit.
- d. *Scanning of references.* Reference lists of relevant publications will be scanned to identify primary studies that were not retrieved through the bibliographic search engines. If eligible studies are found from the list of references, they will be added to the JabRef database.

Each stage of the study selection process will be well documented, in order to make it assessable and reproducible. Thus, the number of studies eligible for inclusion will be annotated, while, for the excluded studies, the reasons for exclusion will be provided.

2.6 Assessing the methodological quality

Each eligible primary study will undergo a quality assessment. The results of a study will be signalled as *having potential for bias* if there is any suspicious of:

- a. *Selection bias:* in situations where there is a suspicion that proper randomisation of the food units was not achieved. For instance, when sampling was undertaken in the context of a monitoring program/surveillance implemented after a food-borne outbreak, or microbiological analysis of food sampled at retail but close to the end of shelf life.
- b. *Aggregation bias* or *reporting bias:* Prevalence or enumeration results are combined for distinct food classes within the same food category (for instance: prevalence data combined for pasteurised milk cheese and raw milk cheese; microbial concentrations pooled for raw sausage and fermented sausage) or combined for samples from different food chain stages (for instance: prevalence data combined for non-filleted and filleted fish).
- c. *Detection bias:* The outcomes of a study will be signalled as being potentially biased if any of the following two situations arises:
 - c1. Detection and/or quantification of the biological hazard is not undertaken using an approved or known microbiological method, or it is carried out using a newly proposed method. However, potential for bias should not be assigned if the study that purports a new method provides an indication of the limit of detection or of test accuracy in comparison to a gold standard.
 - c2. Amount (weight, volume, surface or whole unit) of the analytical sample is not explicitly indicated in the study, but assumed from authors' previous publications, from the ranges of

analytical sample amount provided in the text, or from manufacturer's instructions in case a kit was used.

The results taken from studies that present at least one of the aforementioned validity threats will be marked as potentially biased, in order to perform sensitivity analysis at a later stage during meta-analysis. Meeting a single potential-for-bias criterion will not be considered sufficient to discard a study. However, if a study meets the conditions (a), (b) and any condition within (c), it will be discarded from the systematic review, and the reasons annotated. The two researchers will carry out the methodological quality assessment, and studies marked as being potentially biases will be verified by the senior researcher(s).

2.7 Data extraction from primary studies

The collection of data from the primary studies will be standardised according to the type of biological hazard, this is, bacteria, parasites and viruses. Therefore, there will be three different data models. However, regardless of the type of pathogen, the data to be extracted are related to (i) general framing of the study, (ii) study characteristics relevant to explain heterogeneity in the outcomes; namely the nature of the food sampled and the method of detection/quantification, and (iii) outcome measures, detection and/or quantification.

2.7.1 General framing data

The general framing data are common to bacteria, parasites and viruses, since they pertain to characteristics of the individual study.

Study ID: Unique identifier of the study, defined beforehand in JabRef. Study ID follows the rule "FirstAuthorSurname_AbbreviatedJournal_PublicationYear".

Study type: (a) Survey, for studies whose objective was to characterise or investigate the microbiological safety of food, or its compliance to legislation; (b) Comparison, for studies comparing methods of detection of pathogens; and (c) Other, for any other type of study.

Country of publication: country of the institutional address of the first author.

Year: starting year of the microbiological survey.

Study duration: duration of the survey in months.

2.7.2 *Study characteristics data*

The following study characteristics describe the food sample, and therefore, they are common to bacteria, parasites and viruses.

Food origin: country of origin of the food sample

Packaged status: (a) Packed food, for samples of food contained in any type of packaging, (b) Unpacked food, for food sampled without packaging, (c) Various, for samples of packaged and unpackaged foods, and (d) Not available, when the study does not indicate the packaging status of the food or cannot be reasonably deduced.

Stage: refers to the stage of the food chain from which the sample was taken: (a) Farm, entailing any stage within primary production, (b) Mid-processing, including any processing stage within the reception of raw materials and the end of processing, (c) End-processing, when food products are sampled at the end of production, (d) Retail, when food products are sampled at any retail establishment or vending machines, and (e) Restauration, when sampling is carried out at restaurants or at catering services.

Temperature at retail: refers to the temperature class of the food when sampled: (a) Ambient temperature, (b) Chill, (c) Frozen, (d) Various, and (e) Not available.

RTE status: refers to whether the food produced or being produced is ready-to-eat (Yes) or non-ready-to-eat (No).

Food label: is the name or description of the food sample as indicated in the study.

2.7.2.1 Study characteristics for bacteria

The following study characteristics are specific to bacteria.

Agent: refers to any of the eight foodborne bacterial pathogens.

Serotype/serovar/other: refers to the serotype, serovar or any other distinct variation within a pathogenic bacterium.

Type of essay: (a) Detection, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the pathogen in/on the food samples; (b) Enumeration, when the objective of the study is to quantify the concentration of the pathogen in/on the food samples, and in the particular case of bacteria, when they are determined with no enrichment step; and (c) Both, when the study investigates both detection and quantification of pathogens in/on the food samples.

Detection essay type and Detection essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (culture, molecular, immunological, other), and more specifically, the detection essay. The detection essays within type of essay depend on the bacteria selected.

Enumeration essay type and Enumeration essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (culture, molecular, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the bacteria selected.

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising a hierarchy system composed of a maximum of four variables: category, subcategory, class and subclass (specie or heat-treated status). Table 2 compiles the hierarchical system used to categorise type of food for data from bacteria, viruses and parasites.

Table 2: Food categorisation system for data extraction

Food category	Food subcategory	Food class	Food subclass (Specie / Heat treated)
Beverages	Coffee and tea Juices Soft drink Water Undefined		
Composite	RTE Dishes Sandwich Fast food Undefined	Cooked Raw NA	
Dairy	Cheese	Hard Semi-hard Soft NA	Pasteurised Raw NA
	Fats Fermented Powder Whey		
	Milk	Pasteurised Raw NA	Bovine Ovine Caprine Camel Donkey Mixed NA
	Undefined	Pasteurised Raw NA	Bovine Ovine Caprine Donkey Mixed NA
Eggs	Eggs Egg products NA	Pasteurised Raw Cooked NA	
Fruits	Berries Citrus Drupes	Pre-cut NA	

	Dried Pome Processed Undefined			
Grains	Bread	Cooked		
	Cakes and pastry	NA		
	Cereals			
	Pasta Undefined			
Legume	Dry seeds			
	Nuts			
	Oil seeds			
	Legumes	Cooked		
	Spices	Dried		
	Processed	Fermented		
	Undefined	NA		
Meat	Beef	Cooked		
	Chicken	Mince		
	Pork	Pre-cut		
	Undefined	NA		
	Processed meat	Cooked		Bovine
		Cured		Ovine
		Raw		Pork
		NA		Poultry Mixed NA
	Game	Cooked		Deer
		Cured		Wild boar
		Raw		Other
		NA		NA
	Other meats	Cooked		Caprine
		Cured		Equine
		Raw		Ovine
NA			Rabbit Other NA	
Other poultry	Cooked		Duck	
	Cured		Turkey	
	Raw		Other	
	NA		NA	
Oils				
Seafood	Crustaceans	Fresh	Shrimp	
		Pre-cut	Crab	
		Cooked	Other	
		NA	NA	
	Fish UndefinedF	Fresh		
		Pre-cut		
		Cooked		
		NA		
	Molluscs	Fresh	Cockles	
		Pre-cut	Mussels	
		Cooked	Oysters	
		NA	Scallops	

		Clams Other NA
	Processed	Dry Marinated Smoked NA
Sugars		
Vegetables	Aromatic herbs	Dried
	Fungi	Minimally
	Roots	Cooked
	Sprouts	NA
	Fresh	Minimally NA
	Processed	Dried Minimally Fermented Cooked NA

2.7.2.2 *Study characteristics for viruses*

The following study characteristics are specific to viruses.

Virus: refers to any of the three viruses implemented in the database: Hepatitis A (HAV), Hepatitis E (HEV) or Norovirus.

Genotype: The genotype is a characteristic specific to HAV and HEV. For HAV, the genotype classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV and GVI; whereas for HEV, the genotype classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI and GVII.

Subgenotype: The subgenotype is a characteristic specific to HAV and HEV. For HAV, the classes are A and B; whereas for HEV, the classes are A, B, C, D, E, F and G.

Subtype old genogroup: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the old genogroup classification. The classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI, GVII and GVIII.

Subtype old genotype: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the old genotype classification. The classes go from 1 to 25.

Subtype new genogroup: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the new genogroup classification. The classes are: GI, GII, GIII, GIV, GV, GVI, GVII, GVIII, GIX and GX.

Subtype new genotype: It is only relevant for norovirus and refers to the new genotype classification. The classes go from 1 to 49.

Agent label: It is the description of the virus as indicated in the study.

Type of essay: (a) Prevalence, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the virus in the food samples; (b) Prevalence and Enumeration, when the objective of the study is, in addition, to quantify the concentration of the virus in the food samples.

Detection essay type and Detection essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (molecular, immunological, other), and more specifically, the detection essay.

Enumeration essay type and Enumeration essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (qPCR, reverse transcription-LAMP, digital PCR, RT-qPCR, multiplex RT-qPCR, PCR-NPP, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the virus selected.

Essay identification: Refers to the type of essay carried out for virus identification, in case such an essay was done. Classes are: Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS), Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), and Other for the three viruses.

Essay infectivity: Refers to the type of essay carried out to determine the infectivity of the virus, and it is dependent on the virus.

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising the same hierarchy system as that of bacteria, comprising: category, subcategory, class and subclass (see Table 2), with the only exception that the food categorisation system for virus has one extra variable: Organ sampled.

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: skin, eyes, buccal cavity, gills, corporal cavity, liver, gonads, stomach, bowel, fillets and not stated (N/S). When the sample is meat extracted at the stage of mid-processing, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: diaphragm, meat juice, liver, heart, brain or blood.

2.7.2.3 Study characteristics for parasites

The following study characteristics are specific to parasites.

Parasite: refers to any of the three genus of parasites implemented in the database: *Toxoplasma*, *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium*.

Specie: refers to the specie of the parasite. For *Toxoplasma*, the species are: *gondi* and spp.; for *Giardia*, the species are *duodenalis* and spp.; and for *Cryptosporidium*, the species are: *parvum*, *hominis*, *meleagridis*, *ubiquitum*, *canis*, *cuniculus*, *felis*, *muris*, *viatorum*, spp., and other.

Subtype new: This variable is specific to *Toxoplasma* and *Giardia*, and refers to the subtype information according to the new classification. The new subtypes for

Toxoplasma are: GI, GII, GIII, atypical and mixed; whereas the new subtypes for *Giardia* are: assemblages A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H and mixed.

Subtype old: This variable is specific to *Toxoplasma* and *Giardia*, and refers to the subtype information according to the old classification. The old subtypes for *Toxoplasma* are: Clade A, B, C, D, E, F and mixed; whereas the old subtypes for *Giardia* are: enteritica, canis, bovis, cati, simondi, duodenalis, and psittaci.

Custom subtype: refers to the subtype of *Cryptosporidium*.

Parasite label: It is the description of the parasite as indicated in the study.

Essay sample preparation: This variable stores the type of sample preparation prior to analysis, and it is therefore conditional to the parasite selected.

Type of essay: (a) Prevalence, when the objective of the study is to investigate the presence or absence of the parasite in the samples; (b) Enumeration, when the objective of the study is to quantify the concentration of the parasite in the samples; and (c) Both, when prevalence and enumeration essays were carried out in the samples.

Detection essay type and Detection essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for prevalence (immunological, microscopy, molecular, reference methods, other), and more specifically, the detection essay. The detection essays within type of essay depend on the parasite selected.

Enumeration essay type and Enumeration essay: Refers to the type of essay carried out for enumeration (immunological, microscopy, molecular, reference methods, other), and more specifically, the enumeration essay. The enumeration essays within type of essay depend on the parasite selected.

Essay identification type: Refers to the type of essay carried out for identification of the parasite (molecular, enzymatic, other), and the classes depend on the parasite.

Essay infectivity type: Refers to the type of essay carried out to determine the infectivity of the parasite, and it is dependent on the parasite.

Type of food: the food is categorised utilising the same hierarchy system as that of bacteria, comprising: category, subcategory, class and subclass (Table 2), with the only exception that the food categorisation system for parasite has one extra variable: Organ sampled.

Organ sampled: When the sample is fish, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: skin, eyes, buccal cavity, gills, corporal cavity, liver, gonads, stomach, bowel, fillets and N/S. When the sample is meat extracted at the stage of mid-processing, information must be provided as to the organ sampled, which can be: diaphragm, meat juice, liver, heart, brain or blood.

2.7.3 Outcome data

2.7.3.1 Outcome data for bacteria

The outcome data for bacteria is of three types: general results, prevalence results and enumeration results.

General results

Sample amount unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) cm², or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit, for instance, one strawberry subject to analysis.

Number of samples: refers to the number of samples submitted to analysis.

Confirmation: It refers as to whether the detected or enumerated pathogen was isolated to be subjected to biochemical, serological or molecular confirmation (Yes) or not (No). When no information is provided, the class NA is used.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Prevalence results

Sample amount detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the detection essay.

Limit of detection (LoD): limit of detection of the method if given in the study in log CFU per g, ml or cm².

Detected samples: number of positives samples; and in the case of bacteria, necessarily after enrichment.

Enumeration results

Sample amount enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Limit of quantification (LoQ): limit of quantification of the enumeration essay in log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

Greater LoQ: number of “positive” samples (greater than the LoQ).

Lower LoQ: number of “negative” samples (lower than the LoQ).

[LoQ – 1]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 1 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit, if LoQ is lower than 1 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[LoQ/1 – 2]: number of samples whose counts are between LoQ and 2 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit, if LoQ is between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit; or number of samples whose counts are between 1 and 2 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[2 – 3]: number of samples whose counts are between 2 and 3 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[3 – 4]: number of samples whose counts are between 3 and 4 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[4 – 5]: number of samples whose counts are between 4 and 5 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[5 – 6]: number of samples whose counts are between 5 and 6 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[6 – 7]: number of samples whose counts are between 6 and 7 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

[7 – 8]: number of samples whose counts are between 7 and 8 log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the pathogen in the samples, in log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the pathogen in the samples, in log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

Counts model: refers to the approach used to estimate the mean concentration of the samples that were positive in the detection essay: (a) Impute, if, to calculate the mean, the authors imputed the LoQ value to the positive samples whose counts were lower than LoQ; or (b) Positive counts, if the mean was calculated using only the samples whose counts were higher than the LoQ.

Counts vector {C₁, ..., C₉}: a vector of concentrations of the pathogen measured in a maximum of nine individual samples, in log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration enumerated in a positive sample in log CFU per g, ml, cm² or unit.

2.7.3.2 Outcome data for viruses

The outcome data is for viruses of three types: prevalence results, enumeration results, infectivity results and quality of molecular method.

Prevalence results

Sample amount unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) L, or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit, for instance, one mussel content subject to analysis.

Sample amount detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the detection essay.

Number of samples: refers to the number of samples submitted to analysis.

Detected: refers to the number of positive samples.

Are results corrected for extraction/recovery? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Are results given after drying? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Enumeration results

Sample amount enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Counts unit: It is the unit in which the counts are given: raw genome copies per sample amount unit, log base 10 of the genome copies per sample amount unit, or natural logarithm of the genome copies per sample amount unit-

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the virus in the samples in the unit specified.

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the virus in the samples in the unit specified.

Counts vector $\{C_1, \dots, C_9\}$: a vector of concentrations of the virus in the unit specified, measured in a maximum of nine individual samples.

Minimum: refers to the minimum concentration of the virus enumerated in a positive sample, in the unit specified.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration of the virus enumerated in a positive sample, in the unit specified.

Infectivity results

Total exam: it is the total food samples used in the infectivity essay.

Infectivity (%): Percentage of infectivity in the samples tested.

Quality of molecular method

Inhibition (%): Percentage of inhibition of amplification for the real-time RT-PCR assay. It is assessed with an “external control RNA” - reference RNA that is added in a defined amount to an aliquot of sample RNA and tested using RT-qPCR assay. Comparison of the results of this with the results of EC RNA in the absence of sample RNA enables the determination of the level of RT-PCR inhibition in each sample under test. RT-PCR inhibition levels are used as quality assurance parameters only and are not used to adjust test results. If the RT-PCR inhibition is >75% (undiluted and 10-fold diluted sample RNA), the results are not valid.

Nature of extraction efficiency: Classes are murine norovirus (MNV), Mengovirus, Tulane, MNV and Mengovirus and other.

Extraction efficiency: The extraction efficiency is equal to the process control virus recovery. The “process control virus” is a virus added to the sample portion at the earliest opportunity prior to virus extraction to control for extraction efficiency. If the extraction efficiency is <1%, sample results are not valid and the sample shall be retested. Extraction efficiencies are used as quality assurance parameters only and are not used to adjust test results.

Extraction efficiency range: Minimum-maximum of extraction efficiency in the experiment.

Limit of quantification: Limit of quantification of the method, if provided.

Limit of detection: Limit of detection of the method, if provided.

Replication: Classes are single analysis, duplicate and triplicate.

Warning: To be checked if at least one quantitative result is kept with CT>39 or extra dilution.

2.7.3.3 Outcome data for parasites

The outcome data for parasites of four types: general results, prevalence results, enumeration results and infectivity results.

General results

Parasite unit: refers to the stages of the parasites, and are therefore dependent on the parasite selected. For *Toxoplasma*, the units can be oocysts, tachyzoites, cysts, other and NA; for *Giardia*, cysts, trophozoites, other and NA; and for *Cryptosporidium*, oocysts, sporozoites, other and NA.

Sample amount unit: is the unit in which the amount of analytical sample is expressed: (a) g, (b) ml, (c) L, or (d) unit. Unit refers to the analysis of one entire unit; for instance, one berry.

Basis: stores the basis in which the results are reported, either wet basis or dry basis.

Recovery (0 - ~100%): refers to the recovery rate of parasites with the method employed in this study.

Number of samples: stores to the number of samples submitted to analysis.

Are results corrected for extraction/recovery? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Are results given after drying? Yes/no question to be answered only if stated in the study.

Bias potential: according to the assessment of methodological quality (Section 2.6), results are marked as potentially biased (1) or not (0).

Reason: If results are marked as potentially biased, the reason must be given.

Comments: Any comments relevant for internal validation assessment.

Prevalence results

Sample amount detection: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the prevalence essay.

Detected: refers to the number of positive samples.

Enumeration results

Sample amount enumeration: it is the amount of analytical sample used in the enumeration essay.

Counts unit: It is the unit in which the counts are given: raw numbers per sample amount unit, log base 10 numbers per sample amount unit, or natural logarithm of the numbers per sample amount unit.

Mean concentration: mean concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified.

Median concentration: median concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified.

Standard deviation: standard deviation of the concentration of the parasite in the samples in the unit specified.

Counts vector $\{C_1, \dots, C_9\}$: a vector of the concentration of the parasite in the unit specified, measured in a maximum of nine individual samples.

Minimum: refers to the minimum concentration of the parasite enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Maximum: refers to the maximum concentration of the parasite enumerated in a positive sample in the samples in the unit specified.

Infectivity results

Total exam: it is the total samples used in the infectivity essay.

Infectivity (%): Percentage of infectivity in the samples tested.

Data will be separately extracted by two researchers. At the end, one researcher will verify the conformity of the data extracted by the other. Any non-conformity or doubt will be resolved by the senior researcher(s).

3. Data Synthesis

For each of the biological hazard dataset, meta-analyses for proportions (prevalence) and means (counts) will be carried out to integrate selected information from the different primary studies. As a rule, the meta-analyses will begin with a null random-effects model, and study characteristics will be assessed as potential moderators of the effect measures (i.e., proportion and mean). Important moderators to be tested are country, year, serotype (when applicable), food chain stage and food subcategory/class. Between-study heterogeneity will be also assessed while sensitivity analyses for both prevalence and counts meta-analyses will be conducted to explore the contribution of particular studies (those with potential for bias) to the overall effect size. Graphical meta-analytical tools will encompass (single- and/or composite-) forest plots, Galbraith plots and funnel plots (for testing presence of publication bias).

4. Review Period

The present systematic review protocol was employed to retrieve and extract data from primary studies published between January 2000 and December 2021. In the last bibliographic search carried out in December 2021, covering the period of publication between January 2020 and December 2021, a more sensitive search strategy was applied (Annex 2).

5. Annexes

Annex 1: Search strategies for bibliographic databases used before December 2021

Web of Science

TS=(sampling OR survey OR incidence OR prevalence OR occurrence OR contamination OR level* OR concentration OR count* OR numbers OR presence OR microbiological quality OR microbiological safety)

AND

TS=(Salmonella OR Campylobacter OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)) OR Listeria monocytogenes OR Yersinia enterocolitica OR Bacillus cereus OR Clostridium perfringens OR Staphylococcus aureus OR Toxoplasma gondii OR Giardia OR Cryptosporidium OR norovirus OR hepatitis A OR hepatitis E)

AND

TS=(beverage OR juice* OR drink* OR bottled water OR meat OR beef OR bovine meat OR pig meat OR pork OR chicken OR broiler OR game meat OR sausage OR delicatessen meat OR deli OR poultry OR turkey OR duck OR egg* OR egg products OR dried egg OR dairy OR milk OR milk product OR milk powder OR powdered milk OR whey OR infant formula OR cheese OR butter OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR cream OR seafood OR fish OR shellfish OR crustacean OR mollusc OR mollusk OR produce OR vegetable OR legume OR salad OR fruit OR nuts OR seeds OR sprout OR spice OR composite OR composite food OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR complex food OR multi-ingredient food OR dessert)

NOT

TS=(“challenge study” OR artificial OR meta-analysis OR “systematic review” OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR spiked OR feed OR supplement*)

SCiELO

(SUBJECT:(sampling OR survey OR incidence OR prevalence OR occurrence OR contamination OR level* OR concentration OR count* OR numbers OR presence OR microbiological quality OR microbiological safety))

AND

(SUBJECT:(Salmonella OR Campylobacter OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4))) OR Listeria monocytogenes OR Yersinia enterocolitica OR Bacillus cereus OR Clostridium perfringens OR Staphylococcus aureus OR Toxoplasma gondii OR Giardia OR Cryptosporidium OR norovirus OR hepatitis A OR hepatitis E))

AND

(SUBJECT:(beverage OR juice* OR drink* OR bottled water OR meat OR beef OR bovine meat OR pig meat OR pork OR chicken OR broiler OR game meat OR sausage OR delicatessen meat OR deli OR poultry OR turkey OR duck OR egg* OR egg products OR dried egg OR dairy OR milk OR milk product OR milk powder OR powdered milk OR whey OR infant formula OR cheese OR butter OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR cream OR seafood OR fish OR shellfish OR crustacean OR mollusc OR mollusk OR produce OR vegetable OR legume OR salad OR fruit OR nuts OR seeds OR sprout OR spice OR composite OR composite food OR ready-to-eat OR RTE OR complex food OR multi-ingredient food OR dessert))

AND NOT

(subject:(“challenge study” OR artificial OR meta-analysis OR “systematic review” OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR spiked OR feed OR supplement*))

PubMed

((sampling[Title/Abstract]) OR (survey[Title/Abstract]) OR (incidence[Title/Abstract]) OR (prevalence[Title/Abstract]) OR (occurrence[Title/Abstract]) OR (contamination[Title/Abstract]) OR (level*[Title/Abstract]) OR (concentration[Title/Abstract]) OR (count*[Title/Abstract]) OR (numbers[Title/Abstract]) OR (presence[Title/Abstract]) OR (microbiological quality[Title/Abstract]) OR (microbiological safety[Title/Abstract])) AND ((Salmonella[Title/Abstract]) OR (Campylobacter[Title/Abstract]) OR ((escherichia coli[Title/Abstract]) AND ((shiga[Title/Abstract]) OR (STEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (VTEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (EHEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157:H7[Title/Abstract]) OR (O26:H11[Title/Abstract]) OR (O145:H28[Title/Abstract]) OR (O103:H2[Title/Abstract]) OR (O111:H8[Title/Abstract]) OR (O104:H4[Title/Abstract]))) OR (Listeria monocytogenes[Title/Abstract]) OR (Yersinia enterocolitica[Title/Abstract]) OR (Bacillus cereus[Title/Abstract]) OR (Clostridium perfringens[Title/Abstract]) OR (Staphylococcus aureus[Title/Abstract]) OR (Toxoplasma gondii[Title/Abstract]) OR (Giardia[Title/Abstract]) OR (Cryptosporidium[Title/Abstract]) OR (norovirus[Title/Abstract]) OR (hepatitis A[Title/Abstract]) OR (hepatitis E[Title/Abstract])) AND

((beverage[Title/Abstract]) OR (juice*[Title/Abstract]) OR (drink*[Title/Abstract]) OR (bottled water[Title/Abstract]) OR (meat[Title/Abstract]) OR (beef[Title/Abstract]) OR (bovine meat[Title/Abstract]) OR (pig meat[Title/Abstract]) OR (pork[Title/Abstract]) OR (chicken[Title/Abstract]) OR (broiler[Title/Abstract]) OR (game meat[Title/Abstract]) OR (sausage[Title/Abstract]) OR (delicatessen meat[Title/Abstract]) OR (deli[Title/Abstract]) OR (poultry[Title/Abstract]) OR (turkey[Title/Abstract]) OR (duck[Title/Abstract]) OR (egg*[Title/Abstract]) OR (egg products[Title/Abstract]) OR (dried egg[Title/Abstract]) OR (dairy[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk product[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk powder[Title/Abstract]) OR (powdered milk[Title/Abstract]) OR (whey[Title/Abstract]) OR (infant formula[Title/Abstract]) OR (cheese[Title/Abstract]) OR (butter[Title/Abstract]) OR (yogurt[Title/Abstract]) OR (ice-cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (seafood[Title/Abstract]) OR (fish[Title/Abstract]) OR (shellfish[Title/Abstract]) OR (crustacean[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusc[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusk[Title/Abstract]) OR (produce[Title/Abstract]) OR (vegetable[Title/Abstract]) OR (legume[Title/Abstract]) OR (salad[Title/Abstract]) OR (fruit[Title/Abstract]) OR (nuts[Title/Abstract]) OR (seeds[Title/Abstract]) OR (sprout[Title/Abstract]) OR (spice[Title/Abstract]) OR (composite[Title/Abstract]) OR (composite food[Title/Abstract]) OR (ready-to-eat[Title/Abstract]) OR (RTE[Title/Abstract]) OR (complex food[Title/Abstract]) OR (multi-ingredient food[Title/Abstract]) OR (dessert[Title/Abstract]))

NOT

((“challenge study”[Title/Abstract]) OR (artificial[Title/Abstract]) OR (meta-analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR (“systematic review”[Title/Abstract]) OR (review[Title/Abstract]) OR (extract*[Title/Abstract]) OR (antimicrobial*[Title/Abstract]) OR (spiked[Title/Abstract]) OR (feed[Title/Abstract]) OR (supplement*[Title/Abstract]))

Scopus

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (survey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (occurrence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (level*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (numbers) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (presence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (microbiological quality) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (microbiological safety)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (Salmonella) OR TITLE-ABS-

KEY (Campylobacter) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (escherichia coli) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (shiga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (STEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (VTEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EHEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157:H7) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O26:H11) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O145:H28) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O103:H2) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O111:H8) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O104:H4))) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Listeria monocytogenes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Yersinia enterocolitica) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Bacillus cereus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Clostridium perfringens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Staphylococcus aureus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Toxoplasma gondii) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Giardia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (Cryptosporidium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (norovirus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (hepatitis A) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (hepatitis E))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (beverage) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (juice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (drink*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bottled water) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (meat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (beef) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bovine meat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pig meat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pork) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (chicken) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (broiler) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (game meat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sausage) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (delicatessen meat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (deli) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (poultry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (turkey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (duck) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (egg*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (egg products) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dried egg) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dairy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk product) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk powder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (powdered milk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (whey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (infant formula) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cheese) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (butter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yogurt) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ice-cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seafood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (shellfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crustacean) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusc) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (produce) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (vegetable) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (legume) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salad) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fruit) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (nuts) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seeds) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sprout) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spice) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (composite) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (composite food) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ready-to-eat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (RTE) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (complex food) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (multi-ingredient food) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dessert))

AND NOT

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (“challenge study”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (artificial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (meta-analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (“systematic review”) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (review) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (extract*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (antimicrobial*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (supplement*))

Filters Applied

Years

Type of paper: Articles

Countries: All European countries

Languages: English, Spanish, French, Portuguese

Annex 2: Search strategies for bibliographic databases used in December 2021

Web of Science

TS=(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR “microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence)

AND

TS=(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR “hepatitis A” OR “hepatitis E” OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4)))

AND

TS=(meat* OR beef OR veal OR pork OR "pig meat" OR goat* OR mutton OR sheep meat" OR lamb meat" OR horse* OR chicken* OR poultry OR broiler OR fowl OR turkey* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR game OR venison OR rabbit* OR sausage* OR delicatessen OR deli OR “cold meats” OR ham OR bacon OR salami OR bologna OR hamburger* OR seafood OR fish* OR shellfish OR crustacean* OR mollusc OR mollusk OR clam* OR oyster* OR lobster* OR mussel* OR crab* OR scallop* OR egg* OR dairy OR milk OR butter OR whey OR milk powder OR infant powder OR infant formula OR baby formula OR cheese* OR cream OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR dessert* OR pastry OR cake OR bread OR flour OR flakes OR grain* OR cereal* OR seed* OR oilseed OR nut* OR fruit* OR produce OR vegetable* OR legume* OR salad* OR sprout* OR spice* OR "vegan food*" OR veggie OR drink* OR juice* OR beverage* OR "bottled water" OR composite OR multi-ingredient OR “complex food” OR ready-to-eat OR RTE)

NOT

TS=(“challenge study” OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR “systematic review” OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR “essential oil*” OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR “risk assessment” OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro")

Scielo

(subject:(occurrence OR prevalence OR incidence OR concentration OR contamination OR count* OR survey OR sampling OR “microbiological quality” OR “microbiological safety” OR “microbial quality” OR “microbial safety” OR detection OR investigation OR analysis OR analyses OR presence)) AND (subject:(listeria monocytogenes OR salmonella OR campylobacter OR bacillus cereus OR clostridium perfringens OR cryptosporidium OR giardia OR “hepatitis A” OR “hepatitis E” OR HAV OR HEV OR norovirus OR staphylococcus aureus OR yersinia enterocolitica OR toxoplasma OR (escherichia coli AND (shiga OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR O157 OR O157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4))))

AND

(subject:(meat* OR beef OR veal OR pork OR "pig meat" OR goat* OR mutton OR sheep meat" OR lamb meat" OR horse* OR chicken* OR poultry OR broiler OR fowl OR turkey* OR duck* OR ostrich* OR game OR venison OR rabbit* OR sausage* OR delicatessen OR deli OR “cold meats” OR ham OR bacon OR salami OR bologna OR hamburger* OR seafood OR fish* OR shellfish OR crustacean* OR mollusc OR mollusk OR clam* OR oyster* OR lobster* OR mussel* OR crab* OR scallop* OR egg* OR dairy OR milk OR butter OR whey OR milk powder OR infant powder OR infant formula OR baby formula OR cheese* OR cream OR yogurt OR ice-cream OR dessert* OR pastry OR cake OR bread OR flour OR flakes OR grain*

OR cereal* OR seed* OR oilseed OR nut* OR fruit* OR produce OR vegetable* OR legume* OR salad* OR sprout* OR spice* OR "vegan food*" OR veggie OR drink* OR juice* OR beverage* OR "bottled water" OR composite OR multi-ingredient OR "complex food" OR ready-to-eat OR RTE))

AND NOT

(subject:(“challenge study” OR artificial OR attribution OR sanitizer OR sanitiser OR meta-analysis OR “systematic review” OR review OR extract* OR antimicrobial* OR “essential oil*” OR livestock OR spiked OR biofilm* OR feed OR supplement* OR “risk assessment” OR "in vitro" OR "in-vitro"))

PubMed

((occurrence[Title/Abstract]) OR (prevalence[Title/Abstract]) OR (incidence[Title/Abstract]) OR (concentration[Title/Abstract]) OR (contamination[Title/Abstract]) OR (count*[Title/Abstract]) OR (survey[Title/Abstract]) OR (sampling[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbiological quality”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbiological safety”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbial quality”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“microbial safety”[Title/Abstract]) OR (detection[Title/Abstract]) OR (investigation[Title/Abstract]) OR (analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR (analyses[Title/Abstract]) OR (presence[Title/Abstract]))

AND

((listeria monocytogenes[Title/Abstract]) OR (salmonella[Title/Abstract]) OR (campylobacter[Title/Abstract]) OR (bacillus cereus[Title/Abstract]) OR (clostridium perfringens[Title/Abstract]) OR (cryptosporidium[Title/Abstract]) OR (giardia[Title/Abstract]) OR (“hepatitis A”[Title/Abstract]) OR (“hepatitis E”[Title/Abstract]) OR (HAV[Title/Abstract]) OR (HEV[Title/Abstract]) OR (norovirus[Title/Abstract]) OR (staphylococcus aureus[Title/Abstract]) OR (yersinia enterocolitica[Title/Abstract]) OR (toxoplasma[Title/Abstract]) OR ((escherichia coli[Title/Abstract]) AND ((shiga[Title/Abstract]) OR (STEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (VTEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (EHEC[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157[Title/Abstract]) OR (O157:H7[Title/Abstract]) OR (O26:H11[Title/Abstract]) OR (O145:H28[Title/Abstract]) OR (O103:H2[Title/Abstract]) OR (O111:H8[Title/Abstract]) OR (O104:H4[Title/Abstract])))

AND

((meat*[Title/Abstract]) OR (beef[Title/Abstract]) OR (veal[Title/Abstract]) OR (pork[Title/Abstract]) OR ("pig meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR (goat*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mutton[Title/Abstract]) OR (sheep meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR (lamb meat"[Title/Abstract]) OR (horse*[Title/Abstract]) OR (chicken*[Title/Abstract]) OR (poultry[Title/Abstract]) OR (broiler[Title/Abstract]) OR (fowl[Title/Abstract]) OR (turkey*[Title/Abstract]) OR (duck*[Title/Abstract]) OR (ostrich*[Title/Abstract]) OR (game[Title/Abstract]) OR (venison[Title/Abstract]) OR (rabbit*[Title/Abstract]) OR (sausage*[Title/Abstract]) OR (delicatessen[Title/Abstract]) OR (deli[Title/Abstract]) OR (“cold meats”[Title/Abstract]) OR (ham[Title/Abstract]) OR (bacon[Title/Abstract]) OR (salami[Title/Abstract]) OR (bologna[Title/Abstract]) OR (hamburger*[Title/Abstract]) OR (seafood[Title/Abstract]) OR (fish*[Title/Abstract]) OR (shellfish[Title/Abstract]) OR (crustacean*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusc[Title/Abstract]) OR (mollusk[Title/Abstract]) OR (clam*[Title/Abstract]) OR (oyster*[Title/Abstract]) OR (lobster*[Title/Abstract]) OR (mussel*[Title/Abstract]) OR (crab*[Title/Abstract]) OR (scallop*[Title/Abstract]) OR (egg*[Title/Abstract]) OR (dairy[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk[Title/Abstract]) OR (butter[Title/Abstract]) OR (whey[Title/Abstract]) OR (milk powder[Title/Abstract]) OR (infant powder[Title/Abstract]) OR (infant formula[Title/Abstract]) OR (baby formula[Title/Abstract]) OR (cheese*[Title/Abstract]) OR (cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (yogurt[Title/Abstract]) OR (ice-cream[Title/Abstract]) OR (dessert*[Title/Abstract]) OR (pastry[Title/Abstract]) OR (cake[Title/Abstract]) OR (bread[Title/Abstract]) OR (flour[Title/Abstract]) OR (flakes[Title/Abstract]) OR (grain*[Title/Abstract]) OR (cereal*[Title/Abstract]) OR (seed*[Title/Abstract]) OR (oilseed[Title/Abstract]) OR (nut*[Title/Abstract]) OR

(fruit*[Title/Abstract]) OR (produce[Title/Abstract]) OR (vegetable*[Title/Abstract]) OR (legume*[Title/Abstract]) OR (salad*[Title/Abstract]) OR (sprout*[Title/Abstract]) OR (spice*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("vegan food"[Title/Abstract]) OR (veggie[Title/Abstract]) OR (drink*[Title/Abstract]) OR (juice*[Title/Abstract]) OR (beverage*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("bottled water"[Title/Abstract]) OR (composite[Title/Abstract]) OR (multi-ingredient[Title/Abstract]) OR ("complex food"[Title/Abstract]) OR (ready-to-eat[Title/Abstract]) OR (RTE[Title/Abstract]))

NOT

(("challenge study"[Title/Abstract]) OR (artificial[Title/Abstract]) OR (attribution[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitizer[Title/Abstract]) OR (sanitiser[Title/Abstract]) OR (meta-analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR ("systematic review"[Title/Abstract]) OR (review[Title/Abstract]) OR (extract*[Title/Abstract]) OR (antimicrobial*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("essential oil"[Title/Abstract]) OR (livestock[Title/Abstract]) OR (spiked[Title/Abstract]) OR (biofilm*[Title/Abstract]) OR (feed[Title/Abstract]) OR (supplement*[Title/Abstract]) OR ("risk assessment"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("in vitro"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("in-vitro"[Title/Abstract]))

Scopus

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (occurrence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (prevalence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (incidence) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (concentration) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (contamination) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (count*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (survey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sampling) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbiological quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbiological safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbial quality") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("microbial safety") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (detection) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (investigation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (analyses) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (presence)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (listeria monocytogenes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salmonella) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (campylobacter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bacillus cereus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (clostridium perfringens) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cryptosporidium) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (giardia) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("hepatitis A") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("hepatitis E") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HAV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (HEV) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (norovirus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (staphylococcus aureus) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yersinia enterocolitica) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (toxoplasma) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (escherichia coli) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (shiga) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (STEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (VTEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EHEC) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O157:H7) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O26:H11) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O145:H28) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O103:H2) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O111:H8) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (O104:H4))))

AND

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (meat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (beef) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (veal) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pork) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("pig meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (goat*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mutton) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sheep meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (lamb meat") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (horse*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (chicken*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (poultry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (broiler) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fowl) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (turkey*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (duck*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ostrich*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (game) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (venison) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (rabbit*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sausage*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (delicatessen) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (deli) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("cold meats") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ham) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bacon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salami) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bologna) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (hamburger*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seafood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fish*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (shellfish) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crustacean*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusc) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mollusk) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (clam*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (oyster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (lobster*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (mussel*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (crab*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (scallop*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (egg*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dairy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY (butter) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (whey) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (milk powder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (infant powder) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (infant formula) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (baby formula) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cheese*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (yogurt) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ice-cream) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (dessert*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (pastry) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cake) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (bread) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (flour) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (flakes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (grain*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cereal*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (seed*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (oilseed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (nut*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (fruit*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (produce) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (vegetable*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (legume*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (salad*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sprout*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("vegan food*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (veggie) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (drink*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (juice*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (beverage*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("bottled water") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (composite) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (multi-ingredient) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("complex food") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ready-to-eat) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (RTE))

AND NOT

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("challenge study") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (artificial) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (attribution) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitizer) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (sanitiser) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (meta-analysis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("systematic review") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (review) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (extract*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (antimicrobial*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("essential oil*") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (livestock) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (spiked) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (biofilm*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (feed) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (supplement*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("risk assessment") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in vitro") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("in-vitro"))

Filters Applied

Years

Type of paper: Articles

Countries: All European countries

Languages: English, Spanish, French, Portuguese